

Corrigendum

The author made corrigendum to the article *Conservation Law of Cell Bioelectricity Membrane Area and Ion Inequality Equation Based on Potassium Channel "Origami Windmill" Model* of two clerical errors:

Original content:

The third paragraph of "1.2 Physical phenomena of cell membrane ion exchange", "Action potential, relative to K^+ , rises from $-40mV$ to $+40mV$, which is the process of intracellular K^+ from the L channel uniform deceleration flowing to the extracellular;" "the decrease from $+40mV$ to $-60mV$, is a process of uniform deceleration of intracellular Na^+ from the L channel to the extracellular."

The "uniform deceleration" mentioned twice is changed to "uniform acceleration".

Content after change:

"Action potential, relative to K^+ , rises from $-40mV$ to $+40mV$, which is the process of intracellular the amount of K^+ from the L channel uniform acceleration flowing to the extracellular;" "the decrease from $+40mV$ to $-60mV$, is a process of uniform acceleration of intracellular the amount of Na^+ from the L channel to the extracellular." Among them, the K^+ and Na^+ uniform motion and uniform acceleration motion mentioned in the article mean that the number of K^+ and Na^+ or the number of charges changes at a uniform speed or uniform acceleration, not the real motion mode of K^+ and Na^+ or charge entering and leaving neurons.

By taking the opportunity of the official publication of this paper to corrigendum and declare that it will not affect the conclusions of the relevant papers.

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